

TOSHKENT SHAHRIDA REABILITATSIYANING UY BOSQICHIDA TASHKIL ETISH VA MUROJA'ATLARNI TAHLIL QILISH

Boisov Suxrob Komiljanovich

Toshkent tibbiyot akademiyasi

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14836716>

Tadqiqot maqsadi: Toshkent shahrida reabilitatsiyaning uy bosqichida tashkil etish va muroja'atlarni tahlil qilish.

Tadqiqot materiallari va usullari: 2023-2024 yillar oralig'ida "Reabilitologiya" markazi a'zolari Toshkent shahrida 125 nafar bemorga reabilitatsiya yordamini ko'rsatishdi. Bemorlar orasida xavf omillari, shikoyatlari, o'rtacha yoshi, gender nisbatlarini aniqlashtirish maqsadida maxsus so'rovnoma tayyorlandi va tahlil qilindi.

Olingan natijalar: bemorlarning orasida kasallanish asosan 51-60 yosh oralig'ida ko'proq aniqlangan va 53,6% ni, 70 nafari ayollar (56%) va 58 tasi (44%) erkaklar bo'lgan. Kasalliklar bo'yicha tahlilimizdan bemorlar orasida eng katta qism ishemik insult 68% ni, eng kam Geyno Barri 6% ekan. Bemorlarimiz kasalliklarini asosan gipodinamiya va giperlipidemiya bilan bog'lashadi. Chunki bunday holatda qon quyilish holatlari ko'p uchraydi. Eng kam sababchi deb Covid-19 ni belgilashgan. Simptomlari bo'yicha eng katta foiz bir yoki ikki tomonlama gemiparez va gemipligiya bo'lib 100%, bu ham insultning eng ko'p uchraydigan asoratlaridan biridir.

Xulosa. Demak xulosa o'rnida shuni aytish mumkinki, Toshkent shahrida 2023-2024 yillar oralig'ida 125 nafar bemor reabilitatsiyaga ehtiyoj sezgan, ammo bu kasallanish ko'rsatkichi oldida juda kam foizni tashkil qiladi. Kam qilingan muroja'at bu kasallar orasida reabilitatsiya tushunchasining yo'qligi yoki uning toki funksiyalar tiklanishigacha va ularning mustahkamlanishigacha olib borilishi kerakligi haqida yetarlicha ma'lumot berilmaganligiga ishora bo'ladi. Natijada bu nogironlik foizining ortishiga va davlatning iqtisodiy zarariga sabab bo'lishiga olib keladi.

References:

1. Dam M, Tonin P, Casson S, et al. The impact of long-term rehabilitation therapy on patients with hemiplegia after stroke. *Stroke*. 1993;24:1186-91. doi: 10.1161/01.str.24.8.1186. [DOI] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
2. Dharmasaroja P. Baseline characteristics of patients with acute ischemic stroke in a suburban area of Thailand. *J Stroke Cerebrovasc Dis*. 2008;17:82-5. doi: 10.1016/j.jstrokecerebrovasdis.2007.11.005. [DOI] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
3. Dodakian L, McKenzie AL, Le V, et al. A home telerehabilitation program for stroke patients. *Neurorehabil Neural Repair* 2017;31:923-33. 10.1177/1545968317733818 [DOI] [Free PMC Article] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
4. Duncan P, Richards L, Wallace D, et al. A randomized controlled pilot study of a home exercise program for individuals with mild to moderate stroke. *Stroke*. 1998;29:2055-60. doi: 10.1161/01.str.29.10.2055. [DOI] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
5. Duncan PW, Jorgensen HS, Wade DT. Outcomes of acute stroke research: a systematic review and some recommendations for improving practice. *Stroke*. 2000;31:1429-38. doi: 10.1161/01.str.31.6.1429. [DOI] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]

6. Feys HM, De Weerdt WJ, Selz BE, et al. The effect of therapeutic intervention for the hemiplegic upper limb in the acute phase after stroke. A simple blind randomized controlled multicenter trial. *Stroke*. 1998;29:785–92. doi: 10.1161/01.str.29.4.785. [DOI] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
7. Langhorne P, Baylan S, Early Supported Discharge Trialists. Early supported discharge services for people with acute stroke. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev* 2017;7:CD000443. 10.1002/14651858.CD000443.pub4 [DOI] [Free PMC Article] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
8. Page SJ, Levine P, Sisto SA, et al. Mental practice combined with physical practice for upper extremity motor deficit in subacute stroke. *Phys Ther*. 2001;81:1455–62. doi: 10.1093/ptj/81.8.1455. [DOI] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
9. Siemonsma P, Döpp C, Alpay L, et al. Factors influencing the implementation of home rehabilitation after stroke: a systematic review. *Disabil Rehabil*. 2014;36:2019–30. doi: 10.3109/09638288.2014.885091. [DOI] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
10. Stephens S, Kenny RA, Rowan E, et al. Neuropsychological characteristics of mild vascular cognitive impairment and dementia after stroke. *Int J Geriatr Psychiatry*. 2004;19:1053–7. doi: 10.1002/gps.1209. [DOI] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
11. Studenski S, Duncan PW, Perera S, et al. Daily functioning and quality of life in a randomized controlled trial of therapeutic exercise for survivors of subacute stroke. *Stroke*. 2005;36:1764–70. doi: 10.1161/01.STR.0000174192.87887.70. [DOI] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
12. Teng J, Mayo NE, Latimer E, et al. Costs and consequences for caregivers of early supported discharge of stroke patients. *Stroke*. 2003;34:528–36. doi: 10.1161/01.STR.0000049767.14156.2C. [DOI] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
13. Veerbeek JM, Kwakkel G, van Wegen EEH, et al. Early prediction of functional outcomes after stroke: a systematic review. *Stroke*. 2011;42:1482–8. doi: 10.1161/STROKEAHA.110.604090. [DOI] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
14. Young J. Is it better to treat stroke in the community? *Br Med J*. 1994;309:1356–8. doi: 10.1136/bmj.309.6965.1356. [DOI] [Free PMC Article] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]